

R₁ was more sensitive to thiophanate-M than was isolate R₆.

A special effect was observed with validamycin-A (30% EC, Takeda Chemical Industries Ltd., Japan). Radial growth of *R. solani* was restricted, resulting in the formation of an atypical colony.

In an additional test, benodanil, carbendazim (5, 10, 15, 20 µg ai/ml), and thiobendazole (3, 6, 9, 12, µg ai/ml) inhibited growth of 4 maize isolates (R₁-R₄) and 2 rice isolates (R₅-R₆). ☞

Serological identification of tungro viruses in isolates from 4 states of India

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We collected tungro isolates from Coimbatore and Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu; Cuttack and Simliguda, Orissa; Patna and Pusa, Bihar; and Barrackpore, Burdwan, Malda, and Hooghly, West Bengal, and inoculated them into 15-d-old Jaya seedlings. For serological identification, different isolates preserved under insect-proof conditions were inoculated to 20-d-old Taichung Native 1 (TNI) seedlings at 5 leafhoppers/plant. One week after inoculation, the second leaf of each seedling was crushed in a pestle and mortar with 1 ml of Tris buffer (0.05 M)/10 mg leaf tissue. After homogenation, the sap was refrigerated 1/2 h to settle host particles. The supernatant sap (50 µl) mixed with an equal amount of latex suspension sensitized with antisera to RTBV or RTSV was rigorously shaken for about 1 h.

One drop of this suspension was observed under a microscope (100×) and scored based on clumping of latex particles.

A positive reaction for both RTSV and RTBV was found in all isolates, indicating that these two viruses are involved in causing tungro epidemics in India. ☞

Horizontal and vertical spread of rice sheath blight (ShB)

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Horizontal and vertical development of ShB has been documented, but little is known about disease spread from a single inoculated spot in a field. Highly susceptible Lebonnet was drill-planted in 2.3- × 3.7-m plots with 4 replications. At 20 cm between rows, plant population was 3,500,000/ha.

One plant per plot was inoculated at floodwater level with 1-10 pregerminated (in water agar for 12 h) sclerotia. Horizontal and vertical ShB progression were recorded in centimeters and number of infected leaf sheaths at

5-d intervals starting 7 d after inoculation. Five plants within and next to the hill with the inoculated plant were used to measure vertical ShB development.

All sclerotia initiated infection on the inoculated plant. Horizontal and vertical ShB spread increased from 7 to 22 d after inoculation (DI) (Table 1, 2). The spread was faster from row to row than within row. But the increase was larger within row. At 22 DI, horizontal ShB development reached 93.3 cm within row for some treatments and 90.0 cm between rows.

Inoculum number had no significant effect on spread. All treatments were similar in causing and spreading ShB. It is not clear why the spread from row to row was faster than within row. ☞

Table 1. Horizontal spread of ShB within row.^a

Sclerotia (no./plant)	Distance ^b (cm) from point of inoculation			
	7 DI	12 DI	17 DI	22 DI
0	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
1	0 a	3.2 ab	8.5 ab	22.0 a
2	0.5 a	2.2 a	9.2 ab	37.2 abc
3	0 a	4.5 ab	11.2 abc	18.5 a
4	0.5 a	3.7 ab	14.7 abcd	27.3 ab
5	0 a	1.5 b	6.3 ab	14.5 a
6	0 a	15.3 b	33.8 cd	86.0 bc
7	0.5 a	5.2 ab	19.5 abcd	41.0 abc
8	0.5 a	7.7 ab	23.7 abcd	48.8 abc
9	0.5 a	7.3 ab	29.3 bcd	82.5 bc
10	0.8 a	15.5 b	37.2 d	93.3 c
CV	47.1	25.3	20.3	20.5

^aMeans with the same letter are not significantly different by the Duncan-Waller multiple range test. DI = days after inoculation. ^b3-yr means (1980-82).

Table 2. Horizontal (H, between rows) and vertical (V) spread of ShB.^a

Sclerotia (no./plant)	Distance ^b (cm) from point of inoculation							
	7 DI		12 DI		17 DI		22 DI	
	H	V	H	V	H	V	H	V
0	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
1	6.7 b	0.3 b	16.7 b	1.3 b	23.3 a	2.2 bc	26.7 b	3.2 b
2	20.0 c	1.0 bcd	23.3 b	1.5 bc	33.3 ab	2.7 bc	50.7 c	3.5 b
3	13.3 bc	0.7 ab	23.3 b	2.0 bc	30.0 ab	3.2 c	43.3 bc	3.5 b
4	16.7 c	0.8 bc	26.7 bc	1.8 bc	33.3 ab	2.7 bc	50.0 bc	3.5 b
5	13.3 bc	0.7 ab	23.3 b	1.5 bc	40.0 abc	2.0 b	50.0 bc	2.8 b
6	20.0 c	0.7 ab	36.7 cd	1.7 bc	63.3 d	2.5 bc	90.0 d	3.0 b
7	16.7 c	0.8 bc	23.3 b	2.0 bc	46.7 abcd	3.0 c	66.0 cd	4.0 b
8	20.0 c	1.0 bcd	40.0 d	1.7 bc	38.3 ab	3.8 bc	70.0 cd	4.0 b
9	20.0 c	1.3 d	36.7 cd	2.0 bc	53.3 bcd	3.0 c	63.3 cd	3.7 b
10	20.0 c	1.2 cd	40.0 d	3.2 c	60.0 cd	3.2 c	55.7 c	3.5 b
CV	34.6	40.3	34.2	36.7	45.6	29.7	42.6	30.0

^aMeans with the same letter are not significantly different by the Duncan-Waller multiple range test. ^b3-yr means (1980-82).